



A systemic mixed methods design, incorporating design-based research at school-level (sDBIR) and programme level (pDBIR). Originally developed for an unsuccessful eCubed application in July 2018.

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Please note: The Phases are not drawn to scale. Please refer to the tabular work plan for durations and timing.



INS - the programme that was evaluated

DBIR. Design-based implementation research

sDBIR. DBIR focussed on TPD in schools

pDBIR. DBIR focussed on our research programme

BRMS/PSO/HOCS different learning outcomes focussed tests (reading, maths, psycho-social, higher order cognitive)

IBPA/GIE. Intersectionality / gender- focussed evaluation of research process / data / results.

Class-based assessment: "base/mid/endline assessment using the three instruments; assessment of students for sampled year groups" would have been more accurate.